

PLEDGE

Politics of Grievance and Democratic Governance

**GuiltRoBERTa: A Two-Stage
Classifier for Automated Detection
of Guilt-Assignment Rhetoric in
Political Discourse**

May, 2026

**Funded by
the European Union**

Document details	
Project Acronym/ Name:	PLEDGE
Project URL:	www.pledgeproject.eu
Project Type:	HORIZON-RIA
EU CALL:	HORIZON-CL2-2023-DEMOCRACY-01
Grant Agreement No.:	101132560
Project Start Date:	1 February 2024
Project End Date:	31 January 2027
Project duration:	36 months
Work package:	WP3 Research Framework and Data Management
Authors:	Gabriella Szabó (ELTE Centre for Social Sciences, CSS) Orsolya Ring (ELTE Centre for Social Sciences, CSS)
Reviewed by:	Katerina Mandenaki, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens
Revisions:	3
Dissemination Level:	Public

Document History			
Version	Date	Comment	Modifications made by
1.0	01.09.2025	First draft shared for review and comments	Gabriella Szabó, ELTE Centre for Social Sciences Orsolya Ring, ELTE Centre for Social Sciences
2.0	07.04.2026	Comments provided to the structure and content	Katerina Mandenaki, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens
3.0	27.04.2026	Updated version shared	Gabriella Szabó, ELTE Centre for Social Sciences Orsolya Rig, ELTE Centre for Social Sciences
3.0	11.05.2026	Approved	Katerina Mandenaki, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens

Glossary and Abbreviations	
AI	Artificial Intelligence
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease 2019
EU	European Union
F1 / F1 score	Harmonic mean of precision and recall; a standard measure of classification performance
N	Number of cases / observations retained in a given analysis
OSF	Open Science Framework
PR-AUC	Area Under the Precision–Recall Curve
ROC-AUC	Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve
XLM-RoBERTa	Cross-lingual RoBERTa; a multilingual transformer-based language model
τ	Decision threshold applied to the classifier’s predicted probability for the guilt label

Table of Contents

Executive Summary.....	5
What is PLEDGE?.....	6
How does this paper contribute to the PLEDGE project?	6
Introduction.....	7
Conceptual Background	7
Data Collection and Annotation Methodology	10
Empirical Limitations of Single-Stage Approaches	11
Methods	14
Results Summary	17
Discussion and Applications	17
References.....	20

List of Table

Table 1: Performance of GuiltRoBERTa under different filtering policies and thresholds (gold-standard).

List of Figures

Figure 1: Precision–Recall and ROC curves for guilt binary classification on the gold standard.

Figure 2: Confusion matrix for binary guilt classification on the gold standard.

Figure 3: Confusion matrix for seven-class emotion classification on the gold standard.

Figure 4: Proportion of guilt sentences by emotion in the gold standard.

Figure 5: Performance across filtering policies and thresholds on the gold standard.

Executive Summary

This paper introduces GuiltRoBERTa, a two-stage AI classifier for detecting guilt-assignment rhetoric in political discourse. *Guilt assignment*, the strategic use of language to make opponents feel responsible for moral transgressions, is a pervasive yet understudied rhetorical strategy in quantitative studies. Qualitative case studies hint that it undermines credibility, reinforces moral superiority, and fuels polarisation, but large-scale analysis has been limited by the lack of reliable automated methods. Our approach combines emotion-based pre-filtering with targeted binary classification using XLM-RoBERTa. In the first stage, sentences are filtered for anger, the emotional context most associated with guilt, while the second stage applies a specialised classifier trained on manually annotated Hungarian parliamentary and social media texts. This architecture substantially outperforms direct single-stage approaches, achieving 0.78 precision, 0.95 recall, and 0.85 F1-score on an independent gold-standard dataset. While optimized for Hungarian, the framework is transferable to other languages given sufficient annotated data, offering a blueprint for guilt rhetoric detection across linguistic and cultural contexts. GuiltRoBERTa offers a validated and scalable tool for computational political communication, enabling longitudinal and comparative analyses of guilt rhetoric across parties, policy domains, and time periods. By making both the dataset and model publicly available, this study advances automated approaches to accountability, emotional manipulation, and democratic discourse.

Keywords: political communication, emotion detection, guilt assignment, XLM-RoBERTa, automated content analysis

Data available: https://osf.io/3csgx/?view_only=fe91ba244ffd4a0b8712d527523d0804

What is PLEDGE?

PLEDGE, a Horizon Europe-funded project (Grant Agreement No.: 101132560), investigates the emotional dynamics driving political grievances and their effects on democratic governance. By bringing together researchers, policymakers, and citizens, the project seeks to deepen our understanding of how emotions shape political behaviour and to develop tools and strategies for fostering emotionally responsive governance and pro-democratic civic engagement. The project has several key objectives: to generate knowledge on the emotional determinants and outputs of anti/pro-democratic grievance politics, to generate practical understanding of how the emotional economy of grievance politics impacts policymaking, and to bring together theory and practice and generate tools promoting effective policymaking and communication which can enhance emotionally intelligent and responsive democratic governance.

How does this paper contribute to the PLEDGE project?

This paper contributes to PLEDGE by providing a concrete methodological tool for analysing one of the emotional mechanisms through which grievance politics is communicated, circulated, and intensified. By operationalising guilt assignment as a detectable form of moralised blame, GuiltRoBERTa enables large-scale analysis of how political actors transform anger into claims of responsibility, moral failure, and accountability. In this sense, the paper directly supports PLEDGE's objective of generating knowledge about the emotional determinants and outputs of grievance politics. It also contributes to the project's practical ambitions by offering a scalable tool that can be used to monitor emotionally charged political communication across campaigns, parties, policy areas, and time periods. For democratic governance, the model helps distinguish between legitimate accountability claims and more polarising forms of emotionalised blame, thereby supporting PLEDGE's broader aim of developing emotionally responsive and democratically constructive approaches to political communication and policymaking.

Introduction

In contemporary political communication, emotional and moralised rhetoric has become a defining feature of public debate, shaping perceptions of responsibility and legitimacy. Among such affective strategies, **guilt assignment** plays a distinctive role. It refers to the strategic use of language to portray opponents as responsible for perceived moral transgressions or policy failures. Unlike rational criticism grounded in evidence, guilt-inducing rhetoric relies on emotive language to undermine adversaries' credibility and establish moral superiority (Szabó, 2024). This communicative strategy involves attributing blame to opposing candidates or out-groups, effectively transferring responsibility while mobilising support against those portrayed as violators of shared norms.

The systematic analysis of guilt-assignment patterns has been constrained by reliance on manual coding methods, which are time-intensive and difficult to scale to large corpora. Existing automated emotion detection systems tend to focus on basic emotions (such as anger, fear, or joy), but lack the specificity required to capture more complex rhetorical strategies such as guilt assignment. This limitation is particularly consequential because guilt-inducing language frequently co-occurs with other emotions, most notably anger, making it difficult to detect using standard single-stage classification approaches.

This study presents **GuiltRoBERTa**, a novel two-stage classifier designed to address these challenges through a theoretically informed architecture. Our approach first employs emotion-based pre-filtering to identify sentences expressing anger, and then applies a specialised binary classifier to detect guilt assignment within this subset. The system is built on XLM-RoBERTa models and validated on manually annotated Hungarian political texts. We demonstrate that this two-stage approach significantly outperforms direct binary classification models and provides a reliable tool for large-scale analysis of guilt-inducing political rhetoric.

Conceptual Background

Guilt assignment in political communication involves the strategic attribution of responsibility for negative outcomes or moral failures to opponents or out-groups. This rhetorical strategy differs from rational argumentation by relying on emotive language designed to undermine credibility rather than engage with policy substance. As a collective emotion, guilt can function as a powerful political tool, eliciting emotional responses and constructing narratives that promote accountability while also fostering social divisions (Cokelet & Malay, 2019; Wohl & Branscombe, 2011).

Guilt assignment operates by linking perceived violations of social norms to moral inferiority, thereby affecting both targets and audiences. While such processes may prompt behavioural change, they can also generate feelings of inadequacy when repeatedly employed in political contexts (Alweis, 2003; Brooke, 1985; Gilbert, 2002; Kozelmann, 2007). In political discourse, guilt involves attributing blame to opposing actors in order to reinforce emotional–moral stances and portray adversaries as norm violators (Branscombe et al., 2004; Martinovic et al., 2017; Szabó, 2024).

Political guilt assignment serves multiple strategic functions, including mobilising support, shifting responsibility, and creating divisions among constituents. This rhetoric operates on several assumptions: first, that audiences share an understanding of societal norms and can identify norm violations; second, that exposure to guilt-inducing messages motivates attitudinal or behavioural responses; and third, that those perceived as violators can legitimately be sanctioned (Janoff-Bulman et al., 2009).

Importantly, guilt assignment differs from rational criticism by relying on emotive rather than evidence-based language. While rational criticism draws on data and logical reasoning to foster constructive dialogue, guilt-inducing rhetoric employs emotionally charged expressions to undermine targets' credibility and moral integrity, often escalating hostility rather than promoting informed deliberation. In contexts of political accountability, guilt-evoking language facilitates responsibility shifting and frames opponents as morally deficient, thereby enabling political mobilisation (Hansson, 2024a). Targets of such rhetoric may respond with similarly accusatory strategies, contributing to cycles of blame and communicative escalation (Hinterleitner, 2020).

Previous research has identified responsibility shifting as a central feature of political discourse (Hood, 2011; Weaver, 2018), encouraging further investigation into the emotionalised dynamics of blame attribution. For instance, Wodak (2011) identifies such patterns in the European Parliament, where lawmakers highlight failures of the European Commission to justify their own positions, while Fairclough and Fairclough (2011) document similar “blame games” in UK government discourse. These interactions involve both blame-makers and blame-takers competing to shape audience perceptions, with roles frequently shifting as actors attempt to deflect responsibility (Hansson, 2015, 2018; Van Eemeren et al., 2012).

This literature suggests that while blame and guilt assignment are closely related, blame games extend beyond formal argumentation to include emotional appeals and communicative aggression, often expressed through anger cues (Hansson, 2018, 2024b). Blame externalisation remains politically advantageous despite its potential unfairness, as it redirects public resentment away from political leaders (Hood, 2011). This strategy became particularly prominent during crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic, where responsibility attribution was often distorted and emotionalised, with harm being moralised and guilt disproportionately assigned to selected targets in order to establish moral superiority (Jaworsky & Qiaoan, 2021; Douglas, 1995; Parkinson & Illingworth, 2009; Szabó, 2024).

A related concept is scapegoating, which represents an intensified form of guilt assignment. Scapegoating involves the generalisation and simplification of moral responsibility, disproportionately attaching blame to a specific target group (Campbell, 2012). It is also a well-established social psychological mechanism through which internal tensions and threats to group cohesion are managed by displacing guilt onto external actors (Rothschild et al., 2012).

Guilt-evoking language involves the deliberate induction of guilt in others to motivate behavioural or attitudinal change (Aguirre, 2021). This instrumentalisation exploits the motivational power of guilt to influence how individuals think, feel, and act (Jaworsky & Qiaoan, 2021). Although moral disapproval and guilt induction overlap, they are not identical. Moral disapproval typically reinforces norms through criticism or condemnation, often eliciting guilt as a secondary effect, and thus constitutes a common pathway through which guilt assignment operates in political contexts. Verbal and textual guilt assignment closely resembles blaming in its emphasis on harm causation and the failure to fulfil expected responsibilities (Hansson, 2015).

Political guilt assignment appears across electoral cycles: during campaigns to devalue opponents' moral standing, and in post-election contexts to externalise responsibility for defeat or policy failure.

From a normative perspective, these interrelated dynamics contribute to political polarisation and democratic erosion, as blame-dominated discourse undermines the compromise and cooperation essential for democratic governance (Bachryj-Krzywaźnia, 2021; Hameleers et al., 2017; Meislová, 2021; Schlipphak et al., 2023; Flinders et al., 2024). Hungarian political discourse provides a particularly salient example, where opponents are often morally devalued and framed as threats to national values, thereby constraining constructive dialogue (Kiss, 2021; Sata, 2023; Szabó, 2024).

Existing research on moralised and emotionalised blame has predominantly relied on qualitative approaches, leaving a gap in large-scale quantitative analysis of guilt-assignment rhetoric across extended timeframes. GuiltRoBERTa addresses this limitation by providing an automated tool for the systematic detection of guilt-inducing language in political texts.

Data Collection and Annotation Methodology

The development of GuiltRoBERTa required the creation of a high-quality annotated dataset for both training and evaluation. This section outlines the rigorous annotation protocol applied across all stages of the project, including earlier approaches that did not yield satisfactory results prior to the implementation of the two-stage architecture.

The training data for GuiltRoBERTa were generated through systematic qualitative content analysis of guilt-assigning political language in Hungarian parliamentary discourse. Coding was conducted by two independent expert coders, both native Hungarian speakers with extensive experience in qualitative analysis and political communication research (see Szabó, 2024). Each coder independently analysed parliamentary speeches from multiple political actors, as well as Facebook campaign messages produced by the prime ministerial candidate of the left-leaning opposition during the 2022 Hungarian legislative election. The material was analysed in its entirety to ensure analytical rigour and minimise individual bias.

The coding followed an iterative, multi-stage process. In the first phase, coders engaged in immersive reading to familiarise themselves with the material, producing preliminary notes and identifying emergent patterns. In the second phase, they applied a predefined coding framework derived from the study's conceptual and analytical dimensions, while remaining open to inductively generated categories. This procedure enabled the systematic identification of both explicit and more nuanced expressions of political guilt assignment.

Manual qualitative coding was essential for producing high-quality training data, as it ensured that instances of real-world guilt assignment were accurately captured. Particular attention was paid to distinguishing guilt assignment from rational policy criticism. Annotations required clear evidence of emotive, rather than evidence-based, argumentative strategies.

The final fine-tuning dataset comprised 2,800 sentences: 1,329 guilt-inducing and 1,471 non-guilt sentences, drawn from Hungarian political discourse across multiple sources and actors. One of the most challenging aspects of dataset construction was defining the boundary between responsibility attribution and guilting. To illustrate these distinctions, we provide examples alongside brief explanations of the coding decisions.

Examples included in the guilting training dataset:

The minister failed to listen to experts, and this ignorance caused significant harm to taxpayers.

Voters trusted Viktor Orbán's pledge on affordable housing, and he chose to let them down.

After the damage done to the cultural sector, a morally responsible person would reconsider their policies.

These statements go beyond simple responsibility attribution by framing actions as moral failures rather than technical or strategic mistakes. Guilt assignment is identified when responsibility is linked to norm violations (e.g. duty, trust, moral standards), when the actor is positioned as morally failing rather than merely ineffective, and when the statement implicitly or explicitly invites moral judgement or accountability.

Examples excluded from the guilt training dataset:

The minister delays the implementation.

There is a poor coordination between agencies.

Local authorities did not allocate resources to the project.

According to the coding framework, these statements do not qualify as guilt assignment because they attribute causality or responsibility without incorporating moral evaluation or invoking norm violations and accountability claims.

In addition, an entirely independent gold-standard test set was constructed, consisting of 500 guilt-inducing and 500 non-guilt sentences. This dataset was not used during training. The rigorous annotation procedure ensured both conceptual validity and empirical consistency, providing a reliable foundation for model fine-tuning.

Empirical Limitations of Single-Stage Approaches

Prior to developing the two-stage architecture, we conducted extensive experiments with single-stage models to assess whether guilt-assignment rhetoric could be captured directly using standard classification approaches. Two primary baselines were tested: a direct binary classifier trained on the full dataset, and an extended seven-class emotion model incorporating guilt as an additional category. Although both approaches produced promising validation results, they failed to generalise to independent data, revealing key empirical limitations that motivated the adoption of the two-stage solution.

The first baseline involved a direct binary classification task distinguishing guilt-inducing from non-guilt sentences across the full corpus. Using XLM-RoBERTa Base fine-tuned on 2,800 labelled sentences, the model initially appeared highly effective. On the internal validation split, it achieved a precision of 0.91, a recall of 0.96, and an F1 score of 0.93 at a recall-oriented threshold ($\tau = 0.10$), indicating strong in-sample performance. However, evaluation on an independent gold-standard set of 599 sentences revealed a substantial decline in performance. At the same threshold, results dropped to Precision = 0.53, Recall = 0.78, and F1 = 0.63, indicating overgeneralisation and limited robustness (see Figure 1).

Closer inspection showed that the model systematically misclassified many anger-driven but non-guilt sentences, reflecting its inability to distinguish guilt-specific rhetoric from broader forms of antagonistic language (see Figure 2). Increasing the decision threshold to favour precision ($\tau = 0.33$) reduced the number of false positives, but led to a marked decrease in recall (0.46) and overall F1 score (0.53). Threshold-independent evaluation metrics further confirmed the model’s instability, with ROC-AUC = 0.68 and PR-AUC = 0.58 on the gold-standard dataset—substantially below the near-ceiling scores observed in validation.

Figure 1: Precision–Recall and ROC curves for guilt binary classification on the gold standard.

These results indicate that, while single-stage binary models can learn guilt-related cues within the training data, they fail to generalise to unseen texts, largely due to emotional conflation. Anger is a dominant feature of political discourse, and guilt assignment is often embedded within anger-laden statements. Without prior emotional pre-filtering, the classifier lacks sufficient contrast to distinguish guilt assignment from more general forms of negative rhetoric.

Figure 2: Confusion matrix for binary guilt classification on the gold standard.

To explore whether guilt could be treated as a distinct emotional category, we developed a seven-class emotion model extending an existing six-class framework (anger, fear, disgust, sadness, joy, none) by adding guilt as a seventh label. Unlike earlier pilot models, where class imbalance led to performance collapse, this configuration achieved stable results during internal evaluation, with an F1 score of 0.96 for guilt and a macro-average F1 of 0.81 across all categories.

However, when tested on the independent gold-standard dataset, the F1 score for guilt dropped sharply to 0.26, while the other six emotions retained moderate performance (macro F1 = 0.43). This substantial discrepancy indicates that, although the model could distinguish guilt under controlled training conditions, its decision boundaries diverged from human annotation criteria when applied to unseen texts (see Figure 3). In effect, guilt remained context-dependent: its linguistic realisation is intertwined with moral blame and accusatory framing, rather than constituting a discrete emotional category.

Figure 3: Confusion matrix for seven-class emotion classification on the gold standard.

Moreover, manual inspection of the gold-standard annotations (see Figure 4) confirmed substantial overlap between guilt and other emotions, particularly with anger and partially with sadness. This pattern in the human-coded data indicates that expressions of guilt are rarely isolated, but are instead predominantly embedded within anger-laden contexts. Such overlap further explains the observed model confusion and underscores why guilt cannot be reliably captured as a standalone emotional category.

Figure 4: Proportion of guilt sentences by emotion in the gold standard.

In summary, both single-stage baselines—the direct binary classifier and the seven-class emotion model—achieved high internal accuracy but exhibited poor external generalisation. This limitation is primarily attributable to class imbalance, semantic overlap, and contextual dependency. These findings provided the empirical basis for the development of the two-stage GuiltRoBERTa pipeline, in which emotion-based pre-filtering isolates anger-laden contexts prior to the application of a specialised guilt-detecting model, thereby improving precision and recall in the identification of guilt-evoking rhetoric.

Methods

As outlined in the preliminary experiments, earlier single-stage approaches to guilt-detection proved ineffective due to class imbalance and systematic conflation with anger. These limitations motivated the development of a two-stage architecture designed to capture guilt-assignment rhetoric in political discourse. The task is defined at the sentence level, with each unit labelled as either containing guilt assignment or not. To develop and evaluate the model, we relied on a manually annotated corpus of Hungarian parliamentary texts. Annotation was conducted at the sentence level, with coders identifying explicit instances of guilt rhetoric. An entirely independent gold-standard test set, consisting of 500 ‘guilt’ and 500 ‘non-guilt’ sentences, was also created and not used during the training process.

Two-Stage Architecture

The system combines a general emotion classifier with a dedicated guilt-assignment detector. In the first stage, sentences are processed by an emotion recognition model that identifies expressions of anger, fear, disgust, sadness, joy, or none. Only sentences classified as expressing anger are forwarded to the second stage. This design is grounded in both theoretical and empirical work demonstrating that guilt in political rhetoric frequently co-occurs with anger and blame. The pre-filter reduces noise and increases the likelihood that the guilt classifier focuses on relevant contexts.

Training and Evaluation of the Guilting Classifier

In the second stage, a binary classifier (XLM-RoBERTa Base) is applied to determine whether a guilt-assignment expression is present in the pre-filtered (anger-labelled) sentences. The model was fine-tuned on 2,800 manually labelled sentences (1,329 'guilt' and 1,471 'non-guilt'), using an 80/20 train-validation split to monitor performance during training. To address class imbalance, class weighting was applied within the loss function, ensuring adequate representation of the less frequent guilting category.

Training followed standard optimisation procedures for transformer-based text classification. Hyperparameters (including learning rate, batch size, and number of epochs) were tuned to balance efficiency and stability. After each epoch, the model was evaluated on the validation set, and the best-performing checkpoint was selected based on the F1 score.

Performance evaluation was conducted on an independent gold-standard dataset of 599 sentences, using precision, recall, F1 score, accuracy, and threshold analysis (see Table 1). Rather than fixing the decision threshold at 0.5, it was varied between 0.01 and 0.50 in increments of 0.01 to identify optimal trade-offs between precision and recall. Given that guilt-oriented rhetoric is relatively rare, a recall-oriented configuration was prioritised. The selected threshold ($\tau = 0.01$) provided the best overall balance, achieving Precision = 0.78, Recall = 0.95, F1 = 0.85, and Accuracy = 0.75. This configuration captured the majority of guilt-related expressions while maintaining robust precision.

Expanding the pre-filter to include sadness or disgust resulted in a moderate decline in performance (F1 = 0.79), while applying a stricter threshold ($\tau = 0.10$) improved precision (0.82) at the expense of recall (0.68), as illustrated in Figure 5.

Policy	τ	N	Precision	Recall	F1	Accuracy	ROC-AUC	PR-AUC
anger_only	0.01	128	0.78	0.95	0.85	0.75	0.61	0.82
anger_plus_sadness	0.01	190	0.67	0.95	0.79	0.67	0.68	0.77
anger_sadness_disgust	0.01	211	0.67	0.96	0.79	0.66	0.66	0.76
all_negative	0.01	259	0.60	0.95	0.74	0.60	0.65	0.70
anger_only	0.10	128	0.82	0.68	0.74	0.63	0.61	0.82
anger_plus_sadness	0.10	190	0.76	0.65	0.70	0.64	0.68	0.77
anger_sadness_disgust	0.10	211	0.75	0.65	0.70	0.64	0.66	0.76
all_negative	0.10	259	0.70	0.67	0.69	0.64	0.65	0.70

Table 1: Performance of GuiltRoBERTa under different filtering policies and thresholds (gold-standard).

Notes:

τ denotes the decision threshold applied to the classifier’s output probability for the guilt label. Lower τ values prioritise recall (comprehensive detection of guilt), while higher τ values favour precision (fewer false positives).

N represents the number of sentences retained under each filtering policy

Figure 5: Performance across filtering policies and thresholds on the gold standard.

These results confirm that emotion-based pre-filtering substantially improves downstream guilt detection by narrowing the classification space, while the dedicated guilt classifier achieves near-human-level accuracy in identifying explicit guilt-assignment rhetoric. Compared to single-stage baselines, the two-stage pipeline delivers markedly higher recall and a more balanced F1 score, demonstrating the empirical advantage of theory-driven, multi-stage architectures.

Results Summary

The evaluation of GuiltRoBERTa demonstrates that the proposed two-stage design significantly improves the detection of guilt-assignment rhetoric in political discourse. By combining emotion-based pre-filtering with a dedicated guilt classifier, the system effectively restricts the search space to contexts in which guilt-inducing language is most likely to occur.

On the independent gold-standard dataset, the anger-only configuration achieved an F1 score of 0.85, precision of 0.78, and recall of 0.95 at a recall-oriented threshold ($\tau = 0.01$). This strong F1 score should be interpreted in light of the recall-oriented threshold and the pre-filtered input space; threshold-independent metrics such as ROC-AUC (0.61) indicate that the model's discriminative ability across the full score distribution is more modest. The system is therefore best understood as a high-recall screening tool rather than a high-precision standalone classifier. Nevertheless, the model reliably captures explicit guilt-inducing expressions and generalises well to unseen data.

Alternative pre-filtering strategies incorporating sadness or disgust resulted in lower F1 scores, confirming that anger provides both an empirically grounded and theoretically informed entry point for detecting guilt.

Comparative analyses further show that single-stage baselines—whether direct binary classifiers or extended emotion models including guilt as a seventh category—suffer from class imbalance and semantic overlap with anger. This leads to unstable predictions and limited generalisability. By contrast, the two-stage pipeline consistently outperforms these alternatives across all evaluation metrics, validating its theory-driven and modular design.

Taken together, these findings demonstrate that multi-stage architectures grounded in affective theory can effectively operationalise complex rhetorical constructs such as guilt attribution. The resulting model offers a scalable and replicable tool for large-scale analyses of emotive accountability strategies in political communication.

Discussion and Applications

The two-stage architecture implemented in GuiltRoBERTa demonstrates that emotion-based pre-filtering substantially improves guilt detection by focusing the classification task on anger-laden contexts. By combining an emotion classifier with a guilt-specific binary detector, the model achieved an F1 score of 0.85, precision of 0.78, and recall of 0.95 on an independent gold-standard dataset—performance approaching human reliability. These results indicate that anger-rich contexts provide a particularly effective signal for detecting guilt-assignment language, whereas single-stage or multi-class emotion models are less suited to capturing this phenomenon.

Beyond its empirical performance, GuiltRoBERTa expands the methodological toolkit for political communication research. It enables longitudinal analyses of guilt-centred rhetoric—for example, tracking its evolution during election campaigns or crises—and facilitates comparisons across parties, political actors, and policy domains. More broadly, the study demonstrates how multi-stage, theory-driven pipelines can outperform conventional classifiers in capturing complex rhetorical phenomena. By integrating emotional context with targeted classification, this approach offers a transferable framework for detecting other affect-laden strategies, such as fear appeals or moral grandstanding.

At the same time, several limitations should be acknowledged. Reliance on anger-based pre-filtering may overlook instances of guilt attribution expressed through other emotional registers, such as sadness (e.g. “It is sad to see that the Prime Minister lets voters down again”) or irony (e.g. “Congratulations on your epic fail”). Future developments could therefore incorporate multi-emotion pre-filters or ensemble modelling approaches. While the model is optimised for Hungarian political discourse, its theoretical design allows for adaptation to other linguistic and cultural contexts.

Importantly, the model is not intended as a substitute for close qualitative analysis. Rather, it should be understood as a scalable tool for large-scale text processing. Its outputs can be used to efficiently pre-filter large corpora, enabling researchers to identify high-probability instances of guilt that can then be examined in greater depth through qualitative or comparative methods. In this sense, the approach combines computational efficiency with as much interpretive rigour as possible in capturing the political use of a complex moral emotion that is inherently difficult to identify.

Finally, the automated identification of guilt raises ethical considerations. Responsible use requires careful contextual interpretation and transparency, recognising that not all instances of guilt assignment are manipulative; many represent legitimate calls for accountability within democratic debate.

References

- Aguirre, A. C. (2021). Guilt trip: Emotion, identity, and power in migrant online discourse. *Social Semiotics*, 31 (5), 724–737.
- Alweiss, L. (2003). Collective guilt and responsibility: Some reflections. *European Journal of Political Theory*, 2 (3), 307–318.
- Bachryj-Krzywaźnia, M. (2021). The blame game: Narratives of electoral defeat and party change. The case of four Polish political parties. *Historia i Polityka*, 43 (36), 79–97.
- Branscombe, N. R., Slugoski, B., & Kappen, D. M. (2004). The measurement of collective guilt. *Collective guilt: International perspectives*, 16–34.
- Brooke, R. (1985). What is guilt? *Journal of Phenomenological Psychology*, 16 (2), 31–46.
- Campbell, C. (2012). *Scapegoat: A history of blaming other people*. Abrams.
- Cokelet, B., & Maley, C. J. (2019). *The moral psychology of guilt*. Rowman & Littlefield.
- Douglas, T. (1995). *Scapegoats: Transferring blame*. Routledge.
- Fairclough, I., & Fairclough, N. (2011). Practical reasoning in political discourse: The UK government's response to the economic crisis in the 2008 Pre-Budget Report. *Discourse & Society*, 22 (3), 243–268.
- Flinders, M., Dimova, G., Hinterleitner, M., Rhodes, R. A. W., & Weaver, R. K. (Eds.). (2024). *The politics and governance of blame*. Oxford University Press.
- Gilbert, M. (2002). Collective guilt and collective guilt feelings. *The Journal of Ethics*, 6, 115–143.
- Hameleers, M., Bos, L., & De Vreese, C. H. (2017). "They did it": The effects of emotionalized blame attribution in populist communication. *Communication Research*, 44 (6), 870–900.
- Hansson, S. (2015). Discursive strategies of blame avoidance in government: A framework for analysis. *Discourse & Society*, 26 (3), 297–322.
- Hansson, S. (2018). Analysing opposition–government blame games: Argument models and strategic maneuvering. *Critical Discourse Studies*, 15 (3), 228–246.
- Hansson, S. (2024a). Blame avoidance and critical language awareness: An approach from critical discourse studies. In *The politics and governance of blame*. Oxford University Press.
- Hansson, S. (2024b). Coercive impoliteness and blame avoidance in government communication. *Discourse, Context & Media*, 58, 100770.
- Hinterleitner, M. (2020). *Policy controversies and political blame games*. Cambridge University Press.

- Hood, C. (2011). *The blame game: Spin, bureaucracy, and self-preservation in government*. Princeton University Press.
- Janoff-Bulman, R., Sheikh, S., & Hepp, S. (2009). Proscriptive versus prescriptive morality: Two faces of moral regulation. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, *96*(3), 521–537. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0013779>
- Jaworsky, B. N., & Qiaoan, R. (2021). The politics of blaming: The narrative battle between China and the US over COVID-19. *Journal of Chinese Political Science*, *26*(2), 295–315.
- Kiss, B. (2021). Double resentment: The political communication of Kulturkampf in Hungary. *Politics and Governance*, *9*(3), 227–236.
- Konzelmann Ziv, A. (2007). Collective guilt feeling revisited. *Dialectica*, *61*(3), 467–493.
- Martinovic, B., Jetten, J., Smeekes, A., & Verkuyten, M. (2017). Collective memory of a dissolved country: Group-based nostalgia and guilt assignment as predictors of interethnic relations between diaspora groups from former Yugoslavia. *Journal of Social and Political Psychology*, *5*(2), 588–607.
- Meislová, M. B. (2021). The good, the bad, and something in between: Blame assignment in Czech and Slovak political discourse on Brexit. *Critical Approaches to Discourse Analysis across Disciplines*, *13*(1).
- Rothschild, Z. K., Landau, M. J., Sullivan, D., & Keefer, L. A. (2012). A dual-motive model of scapegoating: displacing blame to reduce guilt or increase control. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, *102*(6), 1148.
- Page, R., & Hansson, S. (2024). Dialogic analysis of government social media communication: How commanding and thanking elicit blame. *Discourse, Context & Media*, *57*, 100757.
- Parkinson, B., & Illingworth, S. (2009). Guilt in response to blame from others. *Cognition and Emotion*, *23*(8), 1589–1614.
- Sata, R. (2023). Performing crisis to create your enemy: Europe vs. the EU in Hungarian populist discourse. *Frontiers in Political Science*, *5*, 1032470.
- Schlipphak, B., Meiners, P., Treib, O., & Schäfer, C. (2023). When are governmental blaming strategies effective? How blame, source, and trust effects shape citizens' acceptance of EU sanctions against democratic backsliding. *Journal of European Public Policy*, *30*(9), 1715–1737.
- Szabó, G. (Ed.). (2024). *Managing moral emotions in divided politics: Lessons from Hungary's 2022 general election campaigns*. Springer Nature.
- Van Eemeren, F. H., Garssen, B., & Meuffels, B. (2012). Effectiveness through reasonableness: Preliminary steps to pragma-dialectical effectiveness research. *Argumentation*, *26*, 33–53.

Weaver, R. K. (2018). The nays have it: How rampant blame-generating distorts American policy and politics. *Political Science Quarterly*, 133 (2), 259–289.

Widmann, T., & Wich, M. (2022). Replication data for: Creating and comparing dictionary, word embedding, and transformer-based models to measure discrete emotions in German political text. <https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/C9SAIX>, Harvard Dataverse.

Wodak, R. (2011). *The discourse of politics in action: Politics as usual*, 2nd rev. edn. Palgrave Macmillan.

Wohl, M. J. A., & Branscombe, N. R. Guilt: Personal and collective. In P. A. M. Van Lange, A. W. Kruglanski, & E. T. Higgins, *Handbook of theories of social psychology* (pp. 296–315). SAGE Publications, Ltd.